

Electrometric Study of Uranyl (II) and Beryllium (II) Complexes of 2, 2'-Dimercapto Diethyl Ether

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Complexation of uranyl (II) and beryllium (II) ions with 2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether has been studied in 40% ethanolic media by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques revealing the formation of 1:1 complex in both the cases. The stability constants of the complexes have been determined at ionic strength $\mu=0.1$ M (NaClO_4) by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. Log K_{stab} values are found to be 12.60, 11.96 at 25° and 12.55, 11.90 at 35° respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the complexation reactions determined at 25° are also reported.

METAL complexes of several mercapto-compounds have been studied by Saxena and coworkers¹⁻⁵ in these laboratories. This paper reports the determination of composition and stabilities of Uranyl and Beryllium complexes of 2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether at 25° and 35° by applying potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques and also the values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS at 25° accompanying the complexation reactions. There is, however, no reference in the literature on the study of the present systems.

Experimental

2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether (referred herein as $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$) was obtained from Evan's Chemetics Inc., New York and other chemicals used were of Anal-R (BDH) grade. The studies were carried out in 40% ethanolic media and the ionic strength of the solution was maintained by NaClO_4 .

Cambridge Bench pH meter and electronic eye type conductometer were used for potentiometric and conductometric titrations. The Universal thermostat U_3 type (Germany) was used to maintain the desired temperature. The stability constants of the complexes were determined from the titration curves of the following solutions adopting Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. (A) 12.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 0.1\text{M NaClO}_4 + 4.2$ mM $\text{HClO}_4 + 40\%$ ethanol, (B) 12.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 2.0$ mM metal ion (UO_2^{2+} or Be^{2+}) + 0.1M $\text{NaClO}_4 + 4.2$ mM $\text{HClO}_4 + 40\%$ ethanol against 0.1M NaOH at 25° and 35°.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the complexes formed between metal ions and the ligand was established by titrating the solutions containing different moles of $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$ per mole of metal ion against standard NaOH. Fig. 1. shows the pH titration curves of (a) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$, (b) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 4.0$ mM UO_2^{2+} , (c) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 2.0$ mM UO_2^{2+} and (d) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 1.0$ mM UO_2^{2+} against 0.1M NaOH. The abscissa 'm' denotes the moles of NaOH per mole of $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of the solutions (a) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$, (b) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 4.0$ mM UO_2^{2+} , (c) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 2.0$ mM UO_2^{2+} and (d) 4.0 mM $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2 + 1.0$ mM UO_2^{2+} against 0.1 M NaOH.

Curve (a) indicates that the protons of -SH groups are not titrable under the experimental conditions. The addition of equimolar concentration of metal ion alters the shape of the curve showing the complex formation between metal ion and hence the lowering of buffer region. The inflexion at $m=2.0$ (curve b) shows the formation of 1:1 complex as explained by the equation:

When metal and ligand were mixed in the ratio 1:2 and 1:4 the inflexions were obtained at $m=1.0$ and 0.5 respectively confirming the formation of 1:1 complex as given below:

and

Similar curves were obtained for Be^{2+} complexes indicating the formation of 1:1 complex.

Conductometric Titrations : Conductometric titrations of the solutions containing metal ions and the ligand mixed in different ratios were also performed against standard NaOH and the titration curves revealed the formation of 1:1 complex in both the cases as obtained from pH titration curves.

Stability constants : The stability constants of the above complexes have been determined at 25° and 35° by applying Bjerrum's method⁶ as extended by Calvin and Melchior⁷. The solutions of $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$ in absence and presence of metal ions were titrated with NaOH from which the values of formation function, \bar{n} and the free ligand concentration, $[\text{A}]$ were calculated. The

Fig. 2. Formation curves for uranyl complexes at (a) 25° and (b) 35°C .

values of $\log K_{\text{stab}}$ were then obtained from the formation curves (Fig. 2) at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and found to be 12.60, 11.96 at 25° and 12.55, 11.90 at 35° for uranyl and beryllium complexes respectively.

Thermodynamic Functions : From the variation of stability constants of the complexes with temperature, the values of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the complexation reactions have been determined at 25° by applying the standard equations⁸ and found to be -17.30 Kcal/mole, -2.10 Kcal/mole and 51.0 cal/mole/deg. for UO_2 -system and -16.42 Kcal/mole, -2.52 Kcal/mole and 43.29 cal/mole/degree for Be-system respectively.

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